

China's Engagement with Central Asia and Dynamics of New Great Game

Malik Firdous, Nazim Rahim, Muhammad Alam

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 01, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 02, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Central Asia, China, New Great Game, Energy Plans, New Ways</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5952026</p>	<p><i>Central Asia and China have been closely intertwined in history and today that relationship is being re-establishing. China's return to Central Asia especially in post-2013 is a landmark in the development of its foreign policy. With its Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) move, this region became the crucial bond for cross-regional trade and infrastructure progress. The purpose of this research is to analyze the China-Central Asia transboundary regional nexus in a geopolitical context. To examine China's strategies in the construction of oil and gas pipelines to meet its energy requirements and to build bases in Europe and Central Asia to transport its finished goods. For this China's ties with three Central Asian states are highlighted along with China's engagement with Europe through this region is discussed in this article. To synthesize the analysis from a theoretical perspective, it is discussed that how China's growing influence in the region can change the region's diverse interests. It has been covered that China's 'New Great Game' differs from classical Heartland theory. Therefore, this study is based on two analyses one is China's energy plans in the form of its energy ties and the second is to construct new ways to transport its finished goods to the world.</i></p>

Introduction

The breakdown of the Soviet Union created prospects for China to get access to Central Asia and the Caspian Region. Geopolitically, the republics of Central Asia are now positioned along Russia's southern border. Geoeconomically, the hydrocarbon reserves of this region are shared by the littoral states of the Caspian Region. According to British Petroleum (2015) the proven oil reserves of Azerbaijan, Iran, Kazakhstan, Russia, and Turkmenistan total 298,6bn barrels (b/bbl), 17,6 percent of world reserves. Gas reserves are estimated at 3065,9 trillion cubic feet (tcf), 46,3 percent of world reserves. Together, the newly independent Republics of Azerbaijan, Turkmenistan, and Kazakhstan hold 18.8 percent of natural gas and 2.2 percent of oil reserves. The geopolitical vacuum left by the downfall of the Soviet Union brought reactions from big powers. The region's huge hydrocarbon reserves have caused strong rivalry, as well as cooperation, among various state and non-state actors, for control over resources.

Central Asia remained increasingly significant throughout the time till to this day New Great Game. Russia and Great Britain remained busy throughout the Old Great Game, still, Russia holds a failing grip but the main actors in today's Great Game are China and the USA. China's "Go West" policy is a wise step to earn capital. Recently Central Asia has become integral to its "BRI, uncovered first by President Xi Jinping in Kazakhstan in 2013, for reviving and expanding the old Silk Road through the new Silk Road Economic Belt (SREB) and the twenty-first-century Maritime Silk Road. With this project, China can expand its ties with Central Asia.

From a Chinese viewpoint, the most significant object for a Chinese presence in the region appears to be the struggle to dominate Central Asia to protect its growing need for oil and natural gas. Moreover, there seem to be vital security reasons for China's efforts to produce a traditional 'vassal' relationship between China and the Central Asian states through investments, trade, and military cooperation. Both the security on China's Western border and her internal security in Xinjiang depend upon peaceful progress in her Central Asian neighboring states and China's relations with them.

It reorganized and expanded its relations with these Central Asian nations to reshape its economic potential through its BRI project. Whereas China and Central Asia were connected through peace, war, and trade for many years, these contacts are beginning to undergo a wide and deep transformation as China has risen powerfully on the global scene. This paper is set to measure the regional and local consequences of China's presence in Central Asia, and to identify the prevailing and future opportunities and obstacles for developing China-Central Asia relations. The analysis is drawn from classical theories bearing on Central Asia and China but also improves the theorizing of globalization and regional cooperation, as well as their interconnections beyond the new China-Central Asia nexus.

The next section will be to review China's dynamism in Central Asia through a critique of the classical geopolitical theories. Here would be highlighted that how china's 'New Great Game' is different from the 'Old

Great Game' of the 19th century. In further sections, there will be analysis of (1) the construction of pipelines from Central Asia to China and (2) the launch and extension of the Eurasian Railroad to carry goods from China's manufacturing bases in its coastal, inland, and border regions. The last section will be a discussion based on the previous analysis, that as China widens its influence within and through Central Asia. China is effectively making Central Asia, a new transnational regional space whose upcoming prominence is expected to surpass its long historical position and role. In a nutshell, China's "New Great Game" is likely to exceed the original "Great Game" in interpreting Central Asia as the new center of the broader Eurasia region.

1. Reexamining Mackinder's Heartland theory

Central Asia is situated at the crossroads between the East and the West and has historically been in contact with a variety of cultures and economies. This interaction made the Central Asian Kingdoms and Khanates the most powerful and culturally advanced regions (Hiro, 1994; Waldron, 1990). Ironically, the history of this region remained volatile in the past but in the current century, it influenced the states' foreign policies. The theoretical source of the region originated in 1904 when Halford John Mackinder introduced his famous Heartland theory. This theory paved the way for the foundation of geopolitics as a field of study and its geographic focus was Eurasia.

He saw the Heartland encircling the rivers' basins of the Volga, Yenisey, Amu *Darya*, Syr *Darya*, and the Caspian Sea as the 'pivot' of influence. He argued that this shield could protect them from external aggression and save the people to live in a united identity. In 1919, Mackinder revised his theory considering the geopolitical realities by enlarging the Heartland area to include the Black and Baltic Sea basins. His theory casts an extensive geographic net apprehending much of today's Central Asia that is becoming a strategic bridge between Europe and China due to China's Belt & Road Initiative (BRI).

Though Mackinder's theory gained much importance but could not escape from critique. Nicholas Spyman coined the term 'Rimland' comprising the European Coastland, Arab-Middle Eastern Desert land, and the Asiatic Monsoon Land. He was of the view that the power of the Heartland could be checked by the peripheral Rimland that those states have an advantage in terms of population, resources, and access to sea whereas the others are landlocked. Mackinder counts the Heartland as more powerful with its location, whereas Spyman asserted that Rimland states (Japan, Britain, and China) would likely become superpowers that those have access to water bodies and greater contact with the outside world (Spyman, 1944).

Mackinder and Spyman made fundamentally geographic deterministic influences, yet their thoughts produced the arenas of geopolitical and diplomatic studies and continue to resound with improvements in Eurasia today. With the disintegration of the Soviet Union, these states got an opportunity to reconnect to Western Europe or turning towards China for economic cooperation (Laruelle & Peyrouse, 2009). By looking deeply into the Mackinder and Spyman theories from the Soviet to the post-Soviet era, we see a shift in economic positions of the states at the western and eastern end of Eurasia, as well as those in the middle section of Central Asia. Out of the Three-World scheme, the former East European socialist countries were considered Second World, and China was part of the Third World. Before 1980 China was in the periphery and rose to the semi-periphery in the twenty-first century (Chirot, 1986). China had resurged to the center of gravity of the world economy that it occupied almost in the sixteenth century well before the appearance of the capitalist world-system (Frank, 1998).

There was no real power in the region when it was ruled by the Timurid Empire during 1370–1405. However, the fragile economic positions of the post-Soviet Central Asian states have formed some kind of vacuum for major powers. China, having returned to Asia's center of economic enormity, is standing to be that power to forge a direct link with Europe through this region. Unlike Mackinder's time, China adopted a new way to make extensive energy links to Europe through its heavy inroads and step up into a "New Great Game" as a stout regional power.

2. Transformation and Endurance in "The Great Game"

China is playing the 'new great game' while stretching Mackinder's Heartland theory. The old great game which was started in 1830 between the British and Russian empires marked the era of tension. They declared Afghanistan as a buffer zone to protect their comfort zones from the incursion of the others. After numerous military encounters comprising two Anglo-Afghan wars, "The Great Game" came to an end in 1895 when the border between the Russian Empire and Afghanistan was settled. It was a time of great powers rivalry in the region which cast a deep impact on the current "New Great Game" in which China is playing a leading role.

The scenario became changed with the disintegration of the Soviet Union where China led the command to control the Russian ex-states. This game emerged with the entry of the United States against its past rival Russia and resource-hungry China in this region. The regional states provided an extra opportunity to the outsiders by their weak systems, corruption, economic backwardness, and also that loss of Soviet support. So this provided extra space for "New Great Game". There are many factors for the sustainability of this game like

the business tycoon's connections in the form of companies, the regimes elite's links to their favorites, kept the theatre alive.

China's entry in this game is the promotion of its policy that is its geo-economic aspects by which it wants to promote its trade links across the globe. For its trade promotion purpose, it needs trade roots that are influenced by Russia who considers these states as its backyard and has control over these links since the Soviet time. This Chinese desire set the stage for this 'Great Game' which welcomes more players to shape the regional settings. China is now a key partner with these Central Asian states and the largest investor which surpassed the Russian influence in the region (Krasnopolsky, 2013). In 2013 by the initiation of its grand project BRI from Kazakhstan it shaped the geo-economics strategy to make the region open and deepen its links to greater Eurasia and Europe. No doubt BRI is a mega project but it has released an opportunity to get benefits from the region and its involvement is a real 'New Great Game'. This paper focuses on the Sino-CA connections which reflect the new geo-economics realities which were not found in the 'Old Great Game'.

It is important to underlie the question that how China gets its foot in Central Asia to make its road to Europe. The importance of Central Asia to China mainly has some valid reasons. It remained a part of Soviet republics which share its legacies and other shared features with China. China's rise through its BRI linked with the geographic proximity of this region justifies this analysis. Beijing is in a position to materialize its objectives of economic development which justifies the examination of Central Asia as the essential path of China's policy.

3. China-Central Asia Energy Nexus

China's regional and global engagements and strategies are mainly driven by its domestic politico-economic conditions. Its volatile economic growth has necessitated the imported energy to fulfill its needs thus it altered the global energy chain in this context. Although its people are not using private cars, however, its usage of gas has been increased and become a leading one of the consumption of energy in the world (*bp-stats-review-2020-all-data*, n.d.).

Although PRC production increased whereas on the other side its consumption also increased over time. Now its booming economy wants it to import more than half of the oil it needs. According to the U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA), China may import about 75% of the crude oil it will consume by 2035. Its dependence on Middle Eastern oil is only expected to increase in the future. The International Energy Agency (IEA) guesses that China will double its Middle East imports by 2035. From among the 15 countries that imported the highest dollar value worth of crude oil during 2019, China is at the top position with US\$238.7 billion (22.6% of overall imported crude oil) ahead of the United States, which has \$132.4 billion (12.5%) ("Worldstopexport," n.d.). As a result, it has become the world's biggest energy consumer in less than 20 years, accounting for almost 20 percent of the world's total energy consumption now. It can be seen in IEA data and statistics that its imports in crude oil have risen ("iea.org/data and statistics," n.d.).

To improve this dependence, China has initiated to expand its international energy sources by supporting the development of China-bound pipelines in Central Asia. Meanwhile, the region's energy policy has become significantly more important, due to its abundance of hydrocarbon reserves and relative regional permanency. Reserves of hydrocarbons, especially gas, are vast. Hydropower capability and deposits of coal and uranium are extra sources. Exceptional wind regimes make the area one of the world's best in wind power perspective, whereas the plentiful sunshine offers prospects for large-scale thermal solar power. These resources could guarantee self-sufficiency and help make the area an imperative market in trading, transport, and sales of energy far into the future. The following Table shows growth in its reserves, China's links with these states will be discussed further.

Table No 1. Energy Potential of Central Asian Countries

Energy Potential of Central Asian Countries							Share of Central Asia in World Reserves %
	Kazakhstan	Kyrgyz Republic	Tajikistan	Turkmenistan	Uzbekistan	Total	
Oil, ^a billion barrels	30.000	0.040	0.012	0.600	0.594	31.246	2.37
Natural gas, ^a trillion cubic feet	100	—	—	100	65	265	4.28
Coal, ^b million short tons	34,502 ^d	895 ^e	—	—	3,307 ^f	38,704	4.16

Uranium, thousand tons U	817	—	—	—	111	928	17.00
Hydropower ^c , billion tons kilowatt-hours/ year	317	99	27	15	2	460	—

^a Proved reserves; ^b World Energy Council definition of "Proved Recoverable Reserves": As per WEC definition is the tonnage within the Proved Amount in Place that can be recovered (extracted from the earth in raw form) under present and expected local economic conditions with existing available technology; ^c Economic hydropower potential; ^d 90% anthracite and bituminous, 10% lignite and sub-bituminous; ^e Lignite and sub-bituminous; ^f 33% anthracite and bituminous, 67% lignite and sub-bituminous; — reserves missing or very insignificant.

Sources: EIA, 2006 and 2008; WNO, 2008; and EDB Industry Report no.2

Central Asia looks close to China owing to its richness of hydrocarbon reserves and the relative regional stability of the area. The area accounts for about 4 percent of global energy deposits. The oil reserves in Central Asia and along the Caspian Sea coast amount to 17 to 33 bbl/d, which are equivalent to that of Qatar. In terms of its energy supply, China turned to Central Asia mostly for two reasons. In addition, with access to a guaranteed and closer basis of rich energy, it wants to contest for its energy security by increasing its "energy diplomacy" with the region. Secondly, developing close links with these states by this energy nexus helps it can deter threats from the separatist activists in its Xinjiang Uyghur province.

China's links to Central Asia are not new but are way back to its Silk Road times for which it established trade relations in 1991 and riding from day today. It sought to form a regional free trade zone, partially as a means of tapping into the constituency's huge energy resources. Its companies like China National Petroleum Corporation (CNPC), China National Offshore Oil Corporation (CNOOC), China Petroleum and Chemical Corporation (SINOPEC), and Petro China are the major investors in Central Asia. It also made a partnership with local companies to contend with the Russian base companies as well as for its energy security. The former Soviet Central Asian space has become an increasingly relevant region to fulfill Beijing's foreign policy and magnificent strategy. For this, it started different energy-based pipeline projects in terms of hydrocarbon development which has significance in Central Asia.

4.1 China-Kazakhstan Energy Links.

Kazakhstan is a very attractive place for Chinese direct investment, both in the exploration and development of petroleum as well as in the production of oil and gas pipelines. Its relations with Kazakh energy resources are essentially different from the situation in other areas, as it is linked to the growth of the domestic hydrocarbon industry in China. For almost 30 years, the heart of the Chinese oil sector was the Daqing Oilfield—along with Shengli, Huabei, and Liaohe (Höök, Xu, Xiongqi, & Aleklett, 2010). In contrast, the most auspicious regions are located in the Tarim and Ordos basins in Xinjiang, which share geological circumstances with Kazakhstan. Consequently, the western border of China became a region of vital interest for Beijing (Guo, 2007).

The first Chinese energy strategy in Kazakhstan began in 1997 with CNPC put its feet on Kazakh soil and explored more oil fields. Firstly, the projection of Chinese petroleum and natural gas interests in the region particularly in Kazakhstan was driven mainly by the corporate accomplishments of CNPC rather than by a conscious and formal diplomatic strategy. This first phase established that energy is not the only attention of the Chinese leadership in Kazakhstan, as border security and social constancy in Xinjiang were also vital.

The largest discovery is the 2,798km long Kazakhstan-China pipeline which transports crude oil from oil fields located in western Kazakhstan to the Dushanzi refinery located in the Xinjiang Province of China. The 813mm diameter pipeline has a capacity of ten million tons a year (mt/y). The CNPC and Kaz-Munai-Gaz, mutually constructed this pipeline. It provided a win-win situation for both Kazakhstan and China by directly linking Kazakhstan's vast oil resources in the Caspian Sea with China's strong oil consumer market. This new pipeline will support China to meet its energy import requirements (See the fig below).

Figure No 1: Oil and Gas Pipelines in Central Asia

4.2 China's Energy Ties with Turkmenistan

Economic relations between Turkmenistan and China are characterized by the total dominance of cooperation in the extraction and sale of energy resources. In the first half of the first decade of the 21st century, Sino-Turkmen trade accounted for no more than 2% of China's total trade with the countries of this region (total within \$ 110 million). The transition of Sino-Turkmen economic cooperation to a new level appeared during President Niyazov's visit to Beijing in April 2006. During that, several treaties were signed, including the General Agreement on Cooperation of CNPC with the Ministry of Oil and Gas Industry of Turkmenistan. According to data for 2016, about 40 enterprises with participation of Chinese capital work in Turkmenistan, about 70 investment projects were registered for a total of more than 4 billion US dollars and 2.3 billion yuan.

Different companies in China have applied several key projects in the gas sector. Specifically, CNPC has many large projects with the state concern Turkmen gas. Since 2008, according to the project on exploration and development of gas on the right bank of the *Amudarya* River, the two largest Central Asia-China gas pipelines from zone A and B operate in the Bagtyyarlyk contract area since 2007 and 2014, correspondingly. After the introduction of the second gas processing plant, the total production capacity of the two plants reached 150 billion a year (Mykytchuk & Hanko, 2018). In May 2014, the commissioning of the third thread C with a diameter of 1219 mm and a capacity of 25 billion cubic meters per year began. Thus, three lines can supply up to 55 billion cubic meters of gas per year to China. China is Turkmenistan's major foreign economic partner, and the Chinese organization CNPC is the largest exporter of gas and, at the same time, the major financier in the field of engineering and technical services in oil fields: drilling wells, well logging, the building of ground services for oil and gas fields, In the same area, SINOPEC is employed to repair and conserve wells in gas and oil fields.

4.3 China's Energy ties with Uzbekistan

In 1992, the 'Economic and Trade Agreement was signed between Uzbekistan and China, whereby they granted Most Favored Nation (MFN) status to each other. In the year 2015, about 20% of Uzbekistan's imports came from China; and about 17% of its exports went to China (Omeliicheva, 2016). In 2013, Chinese President Xi Jinping launched the BRI which would expand infrastructure, economy, and other ties across Eurasia, thus boosting China's inspiration while stimulating early Silk Road trade routes. Kazakhstan is often described as the "buckle" of the BRI, but Uzbekistan could emerge as a practical contender for that role. Since 2017, Uzbekistan has passed a range of market liberalization modifications to increase its economy and make it more attractive for western foreign direct investment. Uzbekistan is developing as a center for Chinese manufacturing, driving the country in pole point to receive Chinese assets.

Uzbekistan's working affiliation with China is not pierced with as many security and economic steepchases as other republics, which also helps it profit from greater relations with China. Trade between the two expanded in 2010, bilateral trade amounted to \$2.44 billion, but this figure jumped to \$6.92 billion by 2019. In 2010, raw cotton accounted for over 50 percent of exports from Uzbekistan to China, but this dropped to under 10 percent nine years later, demonstrating China's rising interest in Uzbekistan's hydrocarbon zone. In

2019, petroleum gas made up for about 47 percent of Uzbek exports to China. Furthermore, Chinese exports to Uzbekistan now comprise machinery and technology accomplished of concluding big infrastructure developments (See the figure below).

Figure No 2: Exports from Uzbekistan to China in 2010 and 2019

China's construction of the Kamchiq tunnel, which connects the Fergana Valley region of Uzbekistan to Tashkent. This 19.2 km long tunnel was built by China Railway Tunnel Group at a cost of US \$455 million. It was inaugurated by Chinese President Jinping and then Uzbek President Islam Karimov on 22nd June 2016. The project is part of the 124 km long Angren-Pap railway line that provides a cheap and convenient alternative to the old Soviet-era railway line, which had to pass through Tajikistan for connecting the Fergana Valley with the rest of Uzbekistan. This tunnel is part of the envisaged China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan railway line.

4.4 China's Engagement with Europe Through Central Asia

The PRC has appeared as a substantial regional power in the 21st century. With high economic growth, military power, and political supremacy, it stretched its wings in all directions. After getting its energy basis in Central Asia, it spread its area of influence directly and indirectly by its wider engagements in the area by its BRI and a bond to link Europe along the old Silk Road. This is the key point where Beijing is leading its increasing influence in many-sided areas as a leading power. Its investment in diverse projects and railroad connectivity are the shows to meet its energy desires. These links not only benefit Central Asia but also spreads to Europe. Its footprints from inside to outside are the actualization of Heartland vs. the Rimland in classical geopolitical theories which promotes the shadow of a new "Great Game".

Beijing's vision comprised to create a network of railways, energy pipelines, roads, and efficient border crossings, both westward—through the hilly former Soviet republics—and southward, to Pakistan, India, and the rest of Southeast Asia. Such a grand network would enlarge the international use of Chinese currency, and "break the bottleneck in Asian connectivity." Moreover, it plans to build fifty special economic zones, modeled after the Shenzhen Special Economic Zone, which China launched in 1980 during its economic restructuring under leader Deng Xiaoping.

4.4.1 Trans-Eurasian Railroad Connectivity

This connectivity is not well managed due to long-distance but China is at a peak in its investment especially in infrastructure. It built widespread transport and infrastructure developments in some of its Asian neighbors and faraway African countries. It started to construct and reinforce its long-distance railroad connections to Europe, to enlarge the overland movement of their traded goods, through its BRI. Due to long-distance and multiple countries and borders, Beijing's exertion to transport more goods to Europe by railroad is an ambitious one. There is a challenge to transfer train cargo from China at the international borders of Kazakhstan and Russia efficiently by moving containers to await trains that spread the cargo to European trains.

The dawn of the 21st century brought new interest for a long-distance rail connection between Asia and Europe, particularly with the thriving Asian trade and the increasing pressure to ship containerized freight in a time-sensitive manner over long distances. These connections are given different names as the **Trans Asian Railway**, the Northern East-West Corridor, the Eurasian Landbridge, the New Silk Road, OBOR (**One Belt One Road**); a term used between 2014 and 2017) or the BRI a term used since 2017). The BRI underlines the importance of China in determining the development of these infrastructure and trade corridors. Beijing is

seeking to enlarge trade relations through Central Asia by infrastructure expansion, including rail connections, inland terminals, and ports (See the figure below).

Figure No 3: The Trans-Eurasian Belt Development

Source: https://www.google.com/search?q=The+TransEurasian+Railroad&rlz=1C1SQJL_enPK913PK913&xsrf=ALeKk00ek5TB4NXbyOO

China-Europe rail connections have multiplied quickly over the past few years as the BRI has been further executed. From 2011 to 2015, many new railway lines (presently nine in total) that directly connect China to Europe started to operate. These are nine railway lines that connect many Asian and European countries with China. The rail networks linking China with Europe is improving the related relationship. These can be seen in the following table which shows the summary of all these railways.

Table 2: China-EU Railway Lines

	Route	Distance	Duration	Start	Frequency
Yuxinou	Chongqing–Duisburg	11,179km	16days	July2011	3/week
Hanxinou	Wuhan– Mělník(CZ)/Pardubice(CZ)/Turkmenistan	10,863km	16days	Oct.2012	2–3/week
Sumanou	Suzhou–Warsaw	11,200km	18days	Nov.2012	6–8/week
Rongou	Chengdu–Łódź	9,826km	10.5days	April2013	1/week
Zhengou	Zhengzhou–Hamburg	10,214km	19–20days	July2013	1/week
Yixinou	Yiwu–Madrid	13,052km	21days	Nov.2014	3xuntilnow
Hexinou	Hefei–Germany	11,000km	15days	June2014	2/month
Xiangou	Changsha– Duisburg/Moscow/Tashkent	11,808km	18days	Oct.2014	Every10days
Haou	Harbin–Hamburg	9,820km	15days	June2015	1/week

Today China is the EU's 2nd largest trading partner, behind the United States and since 2004, the EU has remained China's largest trading partner (Xin, 2014).

4. Conclusion

The situation in the Central Asian region seems to be evolving into a new form of the 'Great Game' that was played out between Great Britain and Czarist Russia in the 19th century, but this is the only one aspect of the freshly developed association (Ahmed, 2002). The Beijing endeavors to dominate the region seems a new version of classical vassal relations and it worked hard to make the area once more under its influence. The principal actors today are China and America, especially following the US intervention in Afghanistan. Neither China nor America worried over Russian weight over the long term, since they know Russia has severe economic and social difficulties of its own to deal with. This can be seen during the US intervention in Afghanistan where Russia followed the US lead and expected financial gains, but also earlier when Russia agreed to share its influence over Central Asia with China through Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO). Beijing's strategy is to use financial means to make these republics more dependent on China, a dependence that

builds on gas and oil as well as politico-military cooperation. This dependence would make it possible for China to build a political and economic base in Central Asia, which makes him a great player.

The practical analysis of China's influence in Central Asia leads me to rethink the guess and angle of classical geopolitical theorizing about the status of this region. Mackinder and Spykman diverged in how they saw the geographic scope of the Eurasian prominence (Heartland vs. Rimland) to Britain's and America's interests, they shared a related geopolitical approach to this region. PRC by the construction of massive pipelines and train services; shifted the understanding of Central Asia away from the geopolitical to geoeconomics. Additionally, the increasing force of these pipelines has initiated to re-center Central Asia or in-between regional space for Beijing to push forward its project i.e. BRI to reach maximum parts of the world.

This China's influence provides more credibility to Spykman's alternative notion of the Rimland where China is a partial sea power. To enhance the continued argument about the theoretical legacy of Mackinder one century later (Megoran, 2004), China's basic role in re-centering Central Asia shows an insight into the realities of the region. It informs to re-evaluate both the allied and unclear boundaries between (a) geopolitical and geoeconomics constraints; (b) the rise of China and decline of old Eurasian powers (c) internal economic growth and external enlargement policy (Xin, 2014).

As compared to the original "Great Game" a "New Great Game" featuring China as the key player produces different outcomes for all parties involved. China's west-wind trains have created a wide channel to extend its trade-related activities. It also facilitated China's "Go West" strategy by persuading more companies to transfer production from the coastal areas to cheaper cities, which opens opportunities for regional development. Similarly, these cargo trains will move China-made consumer goods faster and cheaper by land. Moreover, these trains make it possible for smaller companies (Chen, 2015) to move with full containers. In another overland connection, the current project of China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) from Gwadar Port (Pakistan) on the Indian Ocean to the border city of Kashgar in Xinjiang, if effectively completed and become operational (most of its part is completed in Pakistan) will improve the fastest contact to sea for China's landlocked northwestern area and its Central Asian neighbors (Chen, 2015).

"Sino phobia" may prevent the extragrowth of Chinese trade and investment inside the region. The incidents like isolated riots in Kyrgyzstan against Chinese workers who supposedly had more advantaged working conditions over domestic workers and a fight between Kazakh and Chinese workers took place. On the other side, these republics suffer from administrative problems like corruption, favoritism, and a lack of transparency, which add to their slow economic development that categorized the old Heartland settings (Laruelle & Peyrouse, 2009).

It's a challenge to these republics to maintain the Soviet-era established pipelines due to their poor revenue condition. Another area of concern is instable situations in Afghanistan and Pakistan, where the non-state actors have aggravated the situation that is potentially linked to Xinjiang. In widening relations with the region, China is concerned about its border security, which in turn guarantees constant economic relations in its west (Scott & Alcenat, 2008). There is another difficulty for Beijing that the local workers are feeling inferior with their Co-Chinese workers. The regional states are perturbed over the migrants stay in the city centers. Hence, these republics find itself in a paradoxical situation since it has both labor surpluses and deficiencies, and looking for better working opportunities in Moscow (Laruelle & Peyrouse, 2009).

Concerning challenges and opportunities between this Sino-Central Asia cooperation, Beijing seems to have the upper hand to shape the prospects for both sides. China's commercial activities in the region are significant that will lead the region in a more positive direction. The quicker interlinking between China's economy and global strategy is convoluted further by its shared interests with Central Asia, which could turn the Sino-Central Asia nexus into a vassal relationship branded by a cross-border investment by China for its politico-security purposes.

References

- Ahmed, N. M. (2002). America and the Taliban: from Co-operation to War. *Global Dialogue*, 4(2), 77.
bp-stats-review-2020-all-data. (n.d.).
- Chen, X. (2015). *China's Key Cities: From Local Places to Global Players*.
- Chiro, D. (1986). *Social change in the modern era*. Harcourt.
- Frank, A. G. (1998). *ReOrient: Global Economy in the Asian Age*. Univ of California Press.
- Guo, S. (2007). The Business Development of China's National Oil Companies. *The Government to Business Relationship in China', The Changing Role of National Oil Companies (NOCs) in International Energy Markets*, James A. Baker III Institute for Public Policy, Rice University < [Http://Www. Rice. Edu/Energy/Publications/Docs/NOCs/Pap, 20](http://www.Rice.Edu/Energy/Publications/Docs/NOCs/Pap, 20).
- Hiro, D. (1994). *Between Marx and Muhammad: the changing face of Central Asia*. HarperCollins London.
- Höök, M., Xu, T., Xiongqi, P., & Aleklett, K. (2010). Development journey and outlook of Chinese giant oilfields. *Petroleum Exploration and Development*, 37(2), 237–249.
- iea.org/data and statistics. (n.d.). Retrieved May 4, 2021, from <https://www.iea.org/data-and>

- statistics?country=CHINA&fuel=Oil&indicator=CrudeImportsExports
- Krasnopolsky, P. (2013). Major powers and regionalism in the post-Soviet Central Asia, a research proposal. *University of Nottingham, Ningbo, China*.
- Laruelle, M., & Peyrouse, S. (2009). *China as a neighbor: Central Asian perspectives and strategies*. Central Asia-Caucasus Institute & Silk Road Studies Program Washington, DC.
- Megoran, N. (2004). Revisiting the ‘pivot’: the influence of Halford Mackinder on analysis of Uzbekistan’s International Relations. *Geographical Journal*, 170(4), 347–358.
- Mykytchuk, N., & Hanko, V. (2018). Energy factor in China-Turkmenistan relations. *Epistemological Studies in Philosophy, Social and Political Science*, (1, Iss. 1-2), 96–106.
- Omelicheva, M. Y. (2016). Authoritarian legitimation: assessing discourses of legitimacy in Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan. *Central Asian Survey*, 35(4), 481–500.
- Scott, M., & Alcenat, W. (2008). Revisiting the Pivot: The influence of heartland theory in great power politics. *Comparative Strategy*, 22, 109–129.
- Spykman, N. J. (1944). *The geography of the peace*. Harcourt, Brace.
- Waldron, A. (1990). *The Great Wall of China: from history to myth*. Cambridge University Press.
- Worldstopexport. (n.d.). Retrieved May 4, 2021, from <https://www.worldstopexports.com/crude-oil-imports-by-country/>
- Xin, C. (2014). China-EU trade and economic relations (2003-2013). *Global Economic Observer*, 2(2), 41–55.

Author Information

Malik Firdous

Ph.D Scholar
 Department of Political Science & IR
 Qurtuba University of Science & IT, Peshawar,
 Pakistan.

Muhammad Alam

Demonstrator
 Department of Political Science
 University of Buner, Buner, Pakistan

Nazim Rahim

Assistant Professor
 Department of Political Science
 University of Chitral, Chitral, Pakistan

Dr Muhammad Arif Khan

Assistant Professor
